

Heuristic Evaluation CheckList for Textual DSL

This checklist is designed to be used together with the Process. The Nielsen Heuristics are used in the Heuristic Evaluation Checklist.

The following 0 to 4 rating scale can be used to rate the severity of usability problems:		
Severity	Type	Description
0	Not applicable	I don't agree that this is a usability problem at all
1	Cosmetic problem only	need not be fixed unless extra time is available on project
2	Minor usability problem	fixing this should be given low priority
3	Major usability problem	important to fix, so should be given high priority
4	Usability catastrophe	imperative to fix this before product can be released

Heuristic	Description	Question	Apply	Not apply	Description of each error occurrence	Severity (Check each of the problems found)				
						0	1	2	3	4
H1: Visibility of system status	The DSL should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.	Does the Textual DSL provide immediate and adequate feedback on its status for each user action? For example, after an include or exclude task the language displays a commit message?								
		Do the elements available for the user specifically execute only one command? For example, the "undo" button only performs undo actions.								

H2: Match between language and the real world domain	The DSL must represent the user's language with words, phrases, and concepts familiar to the user instead of system-oriented. It should follow the conventions of the real world, making the information natural and logical.	Are the reserved keywords that compose the Textual DSL used on the user's real world domain? For example, a DSL developed for a domain related to libraries needs to have keywords related to the library domain.								
		Are the elements that compose the Textual DSL a good representation of the DSL's domain?								
		Do the elements that compose the Textual DSL meet the domain goal? The user understands the DSL goal by interacting with its elements.								
H3: User control and freedom	Users often choose DSL functions by mistake and will need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted state without having to go through an extended dialogue. Support undo and redo.	Does the Textual DSL provide a mechanism in order to inform the restrictions of usage in case of, for example, mistyping or committing any kind of mistake?								
		Does the Textual DSL predict wrong decisions made by the users and warn them? For example, when the user clicks on a button for closing all the application and the tasks made by the user were not saved, does the Textual DSL warn the user that the application will be closed and nothing will be saved?								
H4: Consistency and standards	Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing.	Are all the Textual elements apparently connected to each other? For example, are all the reserved keywords shown in the same color?								
		Are all the Textual elements connected to each other according to their names? For example, are all the reserved keywords written in the same style, only using camelCase or								

		only using underscores (_) to separate words?								
		In case of using abbreviations, are all the abbreviations consistent throughout the DSL usage?								
H5: Error prevention	Even better than good error messages is a careful design which prevents a problem from occurring in the first place. Either eliminate error-prone conditions or check for them and present users with a confirmation option before they commit to the action.(confirmation box)	Does the Textual DSL show confirmation boxes when the user performs actions considered dangerous (deleting things, etc)?								
H6: Recognition rather than recall	Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The user should not have to remember information from one part of the system to another. Instructions for use of the system should be visible or easily retrievable whenever appropriate.	Do reserved keywords have a meaningful and easy name so that the user can remember them in a fast way? In this case, keywords are words related to the domain of the textual DSL.								
		Are commons tasks easy and fast to be executed? For example, opening a file or deleting an element.								

<p>H9: Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover from errors</p>	<p>Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.</p>	<p>In case of error, does the DSL show an appropriate error message where the user, after reading it, knows how to recover from the error or where to look for a solution?</p>								
<p>H10: Help and documentation</p>	<p>Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.</p>	<p>Does the Textual DSL have a tutorial in order to provide the DSL's goal, the syntax usage and its meaning, as well as provide examples of the DSL's usage?</p>								
		<p>Are all the commands included on the Textual DSL described in a clear way on the documentation support?</p>								